

A Semi-Micro Modification of Victor Meyer's Method for the Determination of Vapour Densities.

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Few attempts appear to have been made to modify Victor Meyer's method so as to make it suitable for the determination of the vapour densities of very small quantities of substances. The elegant modifications due to Nernst (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1903, 9, 622), Löwenstein (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1906, 54, 707) and Wartenberg (*Ber.*, 1906, 39, 331; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1908, 56, 320) are useful for the investigation of vapour densities at high temperatures. Recently Niederl (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1929, 77, 169) has evolved a micro method, suitable for ordinary ranges of temperature. According to this method, the entire vapourising vessel is filled with mercury and in a preliminary experiment, the amount of mercury expelled from the apparatus, owing to thermal expansion for unit rise of temperature, is ascertained. A sealed capillary containing a weighed amount of the liquid (5mg.) is prepared.

After breaking the tip, it is introduced into the apparatus which is then heated to a known temperature above the boiling point of the liquid under investigation. The expelled mercury is collected and weighed. The difference between this and the amount of mercury expelled owing to thermal expansion corresponds to the vapour liberated. From these data, the molecular weight is calculated. This method lacks, however, the simplicity of Victor Meyer's original macro method, and no other work on these lines appears in the literature.

The modification described here retains the simplicity of the original method while adapting it to measurements on a semi-micro scale.

The apparatus used is shown in the accompanying figure. It consists of a tube A, 9 cm. long and 2 cm. diameter. To its lower end is fused a short tube B, 4 cm. long, 1 cm. diameter, provided with two inward projections P_1 and P_2 . To the other end of A is fused a tube C, 6 cm. long and 7 mm. diameter, having a side tube S, fused near its open end.

The breaking rod R, is made out of 4 mm. glass rod, which is thickened near one end and ground to fit into the top portion of C. This rod reaches almost to the bottom of B and is provided with a small blob of glass P_3 , so that when the glass rod is fixed in position, P_3 is midway between P_1 and P_2 . This corresponds to the breaking device in Newth's ozone apparatus. The fused capillary containing the liquid rests at the bottom of B and is held in position by the three projections P_1 , P_2 , P_3 . By rotating the rod R, the capillary can be easily broken.

The displaced air is collected over mercury in a graduated tube of 5 c. c. capacity. This tube is graduated to 0.1 c. c., the interval between successive graduations corresponding to a length of 5 mm. This can be estimated to a tenth, thus enabling an accuracy of 0.01 c. c. being attained in the estimation of the volume of the air displaced. The ungraduated top portion of the measuring tube is bent at right angles and connected to the side tube S, by means of pressure tubing. A levelling tube is attached to the other end of the measuring tube by a piece of stout rubber tubing.

The apparatus is surrounded by an outer vapour jacket and fixed in position therein by a split cork. Steam is led in through T, and condensed water drips out through T'. The tube T, the side tube S and the ungraduated top portion of the measuring tube are wound round with asbestos string to prevent fluctuations of volume due to a stray gust of hot air from the vicinity of the burner.

A slender capillary of about 2 mm. diameter is prepared and one end is melted down to a rod of about 1 cm. length and 1 mm. diameter which serves as a handle. The other end is drawn out into a fine capillary. In the case of liquids with low molecular weights less than 10 mg. of the liquid was used, the weighing being done correct to 0.01 mg. with a Bunge short beam balance. In other cases correspondingly greater quantities (up to 20 mg.) were used,

the weights being determined correct to 0.1 mg. In any case a sufficient amount of liquid was taken to give a displacement of about 2 to 4 c. c. of air. After filling the capillary with the liquid in the usual manner, the open end was sealed.

The capillaries thus prepared were found to be sufficiently strong and did not burst spontaneously even when heated to a temperature of 40-50 degrees over the boiling point of the liquid.

The prepared capillary was dropped in and fixed in position by proper adjustment of the breaking rod. The apparatus was placed in the steam jacket and heated. An asbestos millboard was placed over the split cork so as to deflect the hot air currents and another was placed between the jacket and the measuring tube.

The levelling tube was adjusted. Generally it was found that thermal equilibrium was established in the course of 5 minutes after the commencement of vigorous boiling of the heating liquid, the mercury level remaining sensibly steady thereafter. The capillary was then broken by twisting the rod R. The levelling tube was re-adjusted and the volume read off, the temperature and barometric pressure being noted at the same time.

In the case of liquids boiling above 100°, the outer jacket was filled with the vapour of boiling decahydronaphthalene.

The results given in the following tables show good agreement with the values required by theory, while there is a considerable economy effected in the time required for the experiment. The compact size of the apparatus facilitates the maintenance of a uniform temperature. The liquid in the capillary, being already heated above its boiling point, vaporises instantaneously on breaking the tube. As the volume can be read off quickly, errors due to diffusion and other accidental causes are reduced to a minimum.

TABLE I.

Chloroform.

Theoretical mol. wt. = 118.4.

Wt. of liquid (mg.).	Temp.	Press. (mm.).	Vol. of air displaced (c. c.).	Mol. wt.
14.3	31.5	759.2	2.99	119.6
8.00	31.5	„	1.69	118.4
16.2	32.0	„	3.44	118.0
11.7	28.2	762.0	2.40	120.1
19.9	30.2	760.0	4.07	121.6

TABLE II.

Carbon tetrachloride.

Theoretical mol. wt. = 153.84.

Wt. of liquid (mg.).	Temp.	Press. (mm.).	Vol. of air displaced (c. c.).	Mol. wt.
17.9	31.3	758.3	2.88	155.6
21.3	31.5	759.0	3.39	157.2
19.9	32.0	„	3.17	157.1
25.3	30.2	760.0	4.05	155.3
15.7	31.0	„	2.51	156.1

TABLE III.

Methyl alcohol.

Theoretical mol. wt. = 32.03.

2.27	31.5	758.0	1.76	32.31
4.10	31.3	758.0	3.13	32.80
4.98	31.6	761.0	4.03	30.73
3.46	31.0	760.0	2.74	31.50
4.85	31.0	„	3.74	32.34

TABLE IV.

Acetone.

Theoretical mol. wt. = 58.05.

5.60	31.5	759.4	2.40	58.37
8.80	31.3	759.0	3.78	58.22
5.08	31.3	758.3	2.23	57.02
3.08	30.6	760.0	1.35	56.84
3.81	30.6	„	1.65	57.51

TABLE V.

Chlorobenzene.

Theoretical mol. wt. = 112.5.

Wt. of liquid (mg.).	Temp.	Press. (mm.).	Vol. of air displaced (c. c.).	Mol. wt.
7.90	31.8	758.0	1.72	115.2
14.4	33.1	759.5	3.09	117.1
15.0	33.0	761.0	3.36	111.9
14.7	32.3	758.0	3.24	114.0
12.7	32.2	..	2.83	112.7

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